

Tellme: From user to developer in one click

Derya Özçelik-Buskermolen¹

derya.ozcelik-buskermolen@oce.com

Abbie Vanhoutte¹

abbie.vanhoutte@oce.com

Andrea Meessen¹

andrea.meessen@oce.com

Ruben Hekkens¹

ruben.hekkens@oce.com

Nanne Krikke¹

nanne.krikke@oce.com

Merijn Neeleman¹

merijn.neeleman@oce.com

¹Océ Technologies, the Netherlands

Abstract Tellme is a new user research tool that connects qualitative user feedback to quantitative product data in business-to-business environments. The concept consists of a mobile application and a dashboard. Through the mobile application qualitative user feedback is obtained during prolonged use of products. This feedback is connected to the quantitative product data of these products (data logging) and shown real-time to the design and development team via a monitoring dashboard. As such the development team can not only empathize with the users they are designing for, but also immediately address the obtained feedback during development. This increases the probability that the end-product will fulfill the end-user's needs and expectations.

In this paper we will first discuss our motivation to develop Tellme. We will give an overview of existing tools and methods related to Tellme. We will introduce Tellme and report a case where Tellme was used. We will conclude the paper by discussing its use in new product development processes.

Keywords *Empathy, Customer intimacy, Product validation, B2B user research, User research tools*

Introduction

At Océ – a Canon Company, we are developing professional print systems that are used in commercial contexts by professional users. We acknowledge that for making the right product, it is crucial to obtain knowledge about users, their environments and their experiences with our products. User-centered design is the core of our new product development processes. We use established methods and tools like contextual inquiry, personas, usability testing and product validations at customer sites before our products are released. However, new product development processes are changing. The pressure on time-to-market is increasing, leading to a tension between research and development. To pursue our user-centered approach we need to have means to easily get feedback from users and to communicate this feedback quickly and effectively to the development teams.

Developers often base their assessment of product success mainly on statistics (product data): if the numbers are right, the product must be working correctly. Being able to monitor critical product parameters remotely is an innovation that helps developers to improve products in a quick way, yet it does not help them to understand the everyday reality of users. For this purpose we have developed Tellme.

Through Tellme the reality of a product's parameters captured in quantitative product data is combined with rich insights provided by the product's users. By aggregating and communicating this information directly to the development team, a dialogue between user, product data and developer is created. The developers not only get a comprehensive overview of

the product's performance, but they are also enabled to understand and empathize with the users. Based on these insights, necessary improvements can already be implemented during product development. This saves time and resources and increases the likelihood that the end-product will fulfill the users' needs and expectations.

In this paper we will first discuss our motivation to develop Tellme. We will give an overview of existing tools and methods related to Tellme. We will introduce Tellme and report a case where Tellme was used. We will conclude the paper by discussing its value in new product development processes.

Challenges of doing user research in B2B contexts

Océ develops professional print systems for business-to-business (B2B) environments. Following a user-centered design process in a B2B context brings along some challenges.

In a B2B context, end-users are trained professionals. They have specific expertise and advanced tasks and responsibilities. It is therefore more difficult for designers to understand and empathize with such professionals, because their experience, expertise and mind-set are different. Designers need to be informed very well about the users they are designing for, in order to know their activities and understand their needs.

In a B2C context the user who provides the budget, considers options, makes the decision to purchase, purchases and uses the product, is one single person. However, in a B2B context different stakeholders are

involved in each stage. Even though the end-user experience is still in the focus, the needs and expectations of all these stakeholders should be considered during a new product development process (Nielsen, 2006).

Reaching the end-users, getting their commitment and motivating them to participate in user research can also be cumbersome. Different channels such as business units, sales organizations, service organizations and the users' management, are inquired to establish contact with end-users. This long path de-motivates design professionals and makes them incline to get user feedback indirectly from user representatives and/or experts (Özçelik et al., 2011). This however involves the risk of filtered and biased information.

Since it concerns their professional activities, getting end-users' motivation to participate in user research is also challenging. On the one hand, they appreciate being asked for their opinion; on the other hand, the research is of secondary importance as their daily work will always have priority.

Another challenge lies in the products' nature. Products developed for B2B contexts are professional products. They have complex specifications, are integrated in a specific workflow and are used with other products and software systems. These products are used by different end-users who have different roles in a workflow. This complexity strengthens the importance of user-centered design and usability in a B2B context (Nielsen, 2006); however, it brings also the strong need to have a thorough understanding of the professional contexts and related workflows.

Nowadays data logging is widely used by companies, especially in B2B contexts, to get insights in the usage patterns of products. Intelligence built in these products sends data about pre-determined areas of interest; such as volume of production, number of errors and consumption of resources. Even though data logging provides continuous flows of large amounts of data, it has some limitations. Firstly, it cannot capture unexpected insights because the data which would be extracted from the device should be coded beforehand. Secondly, it provides insights only regarding quantifiable measures and can only support product development regarding those aspects. For example, it is difficult to capture experiential and affective aspects of user experience through data logging.

All these challenges, together with the desire to bring breakthrough products to the market with decreasing lead times, require us to update our portfolio of user research tools and methods. The development of Tellme is motivated by these concerns.

The tools and methods used in user-centered design processes at Océ

In order to understand our professional users and their latent needs, we use several methods. Amongst those are contextual inquiries, cultural probes and beta testing.

With the contextual inquiry method (Holtzblatt and Jones, 1993), we interview end-users and observe their ongoing work in their natural work contexts. During a full day, an employee from Research and Development (R&D) observes professional users at work in a print production environment. The contextual inquiry method allows us to examine and describe actual workflows of customers in detail. Information is gathered on how work is done with the tools at hand. The generated data are very rich and effectively communicating insights to the development team is a challenge.

Cultural probes (Gaver, Dunne and Pacenti, 1999) are another tool to gather information about end-users. Users are given booklets containing a small amount of creative assignments that encourage them to reflect on their experience with a certain product. However, we also experience some limitations which are also mentioned by Lucero and Mattelmaki (2007). It takes time of the participants during their working hours. Next to that, there is neither dialogue nor interaction with the participants during the period they fill in the booklets. We never know whether they are using the probes as instructed until we get the results. Moreover, there might be urgent feedback, but this can only be addressed after the research period.

To validate whether our products fit within the complex environments of our customers, we conduct beta tests. During a beta test a product is exposed to the real world and tested by target users. In the later phases of a development process, a small number of prototypes are placed at selected customer sites. The customer commits to using the product for a couple of weeks and giving feedback on the strong points and what should be improved before the final product is introduced to the market. At several moments during this process, we conduct interviews with users. Based on this, several improvements can be implemented in the final product. Next to that, features for the second iteration and ideas for future products are inspired by the feedback of users. In this respect, ensuring a continuous feedback flow from users to the development team is really crucial. In practice however, this is often challenging. Not everybody from the development team can visit the customer sites, so it is hard to transfer the real customer knowledge to the whole development team. As time and resources for improvements are limited, it is crucial to highlight the most important issues and to convince the developers to take initiatives to improve them.

Tellme tackles the limitations of the current user-centered design research tools used by Océ. It enables our users to communicate their feedback real-time to the development team, in an interactive and effective way. As such we create a comprehensive dialogue with users at customer environments.

Tellme: creating a dialogue between users, product data and developers

Tellme consists of a mobile application that is used by end-users, and a monitoring dashboard for the development team. A moderator facilitates the connection between both.

Figure 1. Tellme mobile application.

The mobile application

The Tellme App is a qualitative research tool that runs on a smart phone. Via the application, end-users at customer sites can directly provide feedback about their experiences with our products. Depending on the time they have, the message they want to send, or their personal preferences to communicate, they can choose different means to communicate their feedback: responding to built-in surveys, sharing ad-hoc feedback, sending pictures and expressing emotions with smiley's (Figure 1). The development team can respond to this feedback by asking further questions and giving tips to optimize the user's experience.

The survey - based on the method of cultural probes - consists of questions and assignments prepared by a user researcher in the development team. During the study, every day one question becomes available for the participants. When the question is available, its color turns green on the main screen. Answered questions are marked blue and pending questions are marked orange. As such, the progress of the participant is made visible.

Participants can also directly share their ad-hoc feedback with the development team at any time during the research. They can attach pictures and movies to better explain their point. Next to that, participants can also express their emotions by means of smileys, with the option to explain their choice for a certain emotion. Finally, participants can receive ad-hoc questions from the development team. They can answer the question by means of a text message, when desired, accompanied by pictures or videos. Participants also receive tips from the development team which can help them to use the product in a more easy and efficient way. This two-way communication and personal attention motivates the participants to provide continuous and rich feedback. The feedback that is generated via the application provides deep and rich insights in the experiences of the users of our products.

The monitoring dashboard

The Tellme dashboard (Figure 2) shows an overview of the user feedback gathered through the mobile application, combined with printer data that are collected via logging. Logging is a technique that is used in combination with an electronic device, which automatically collects data by a system or a server (Schmid, 2012). This combination of both quantitative and qualitative information gives a unique insight into the product's performance and at the same time how users are experiencing the product.

In the dashboard, the emotional expressions indicating the mood of the participants are mapped on the quantitative data logged from the product. Next to that, a time-line with messages and images is presented. Furthermore, the dashboard shows the survey results, visualized in word clouds. Positive and negative remarks are clustered per topic. The participants' replies to the ad-hoc questions are also presented, together with their feedback and the pictures shared via the application. The home screen shows the general overview, while detailed information can be reached through navigating to sub-screens (Figure 3).

To make sure the development team can directly see the feedback coming from the customer sites, the dashboard is presented on a big touch screen placed in the project room (Figure 4) and can also be reached via an internal webpage. Rich infographics give the development team a real-time overview of the users' actual experience (qualitative information) combined with the product's performance (quantitative data). These direct insights allow the development team to empathize with the users, to comprehend their feedback and to understand the context of the product they are developing. This inspires and supports the development team to make the right choices, based on real use cases and user feedback.

Figure 2. Tellme monitoring dashboard.

Figure 3. Ub-screen of the dashboard showing the feedback of users on different aspects.

Figure 4. Development team looking at the Tellme dashboard in the project room.

The moderator

The two-way flow of information between the mobile application and the dashboard is managed by a moderator. This person is an independent user researcher, who works for the development team and who leads the user study. The workflow is shown in Figure 5.

Accordingly,

- Moderator defines questions and sends them to the user via the app
- The user answers the questions (at his/her convenience)
- This feedback is sent to the moderator via the app
- The moderator analyses and clusters the information, decides what and how to present it (e.g. word cloud, clusters, timeline) and forwards this info on the dashboard
- Data logging from the printer is sent directly to the dashboard
- The development team looks at the dashboard, interprets it and this inspires extra questions and/or advice for the users
- These ad hoc questions and/or advice are sent to the user via the app through the moderator

Relation to existing tools and methods

Tellme is strongly related to cultural probes. Since they have been introduced, cultural probes are widely embraced by the design research community. However, they have also evolved resulting from the adaptation of the tool to the needs of the research. Literature research reveals divergent uses of cultural probes and related tools derived from them (Boehner et al., 2007). Especially internet and advancement of smart technologies leads to a new generation of, more technology based, probes; such as technology probes (Hutchinson et al., 2003) and mobile probes (Hulkko et al., 2004). These probes are mainly used as means to collect information from users through the use of available technology. Today smart phones provide a wide range of means to collect information through the use of technology embedded in them; such as cameras, GPS and sensors. While developing the Tellme App, we were inspired by probes as a method of data collection and we used smart phones as means to achieve that. However, the Tellme concept is more than just the Tellme App. The data collected through the application is coupled to the Tellme dashboard.

Figure 5. The workflow of Tellme.

Case study

The study

Tellme was used to validate a new print system of Océ. A first version of this product was installed at a selected number of customer sites. The goal of this study was twofold: to get user feedback on the product and to get user feedback on the Tellme concept. In this paper we will only share the feedback on Tellme.

The study was conducted in the early phases of the development of Tellme. A prototype of the Tellme App and Dashboard were used in the study (Figure 6).

The study was conducted with 8 participants at 3 print production sites. One site was an internal Océ R&D environment, where hired print operators operated the product for the purpose of testing. The other two were customer sites where the new printer was recently installed. All participants were professional operators working in shifts. They used the Tellme App during their work. The development team of Océ also participated in the study, as users of the Tellme Dashboard. A usability designer from the Océ Design department was the moderator in this study.

The Tellme App was installed on phones owned by Océ and provided to the participants. Two phones were used per customer site. The study in the different sites was carried out in sequence and lasted one week per site. Users were informed about the research up front. They were explained that the information and the multimedia materials they sent would be visible to the development team, but for internal use only.

The Tellme Dashboard was placed in the project room of the development team. Part of the feedback coming from users was shown directly on the dashboard; such as the smileys and the word clouds. Other feedback, such as opinions and experiences, was first analyzed by the moderator and then posted on the dashboard in an organized way.

Figure 6. Prototype of Tellme mobile application (left) and dashboard (right).

Findings and discussion

We collected feedback on Tellme from the operators (users of the app), as well as the development team (users of the dashboard). The feedback from all 8 operators was collected by means of an interview by telephone during the test period (10 minutes) and a face-to-face interview at the end of the test (30 minutes). The topics included a.o. their general experiences, pro and contra, usability, suggestions for improvements. Some operators also sent feedback by means of the app. Feedback of 8 engineers from the development team was collected during and after the study by short, individual, face-to-face interviews. Below, the findings based on this feedback are described.

Users

From this study we learned that operators appreciated the Tellme App and found it easy to use. Giving feedback by means of the app was perceived as ‘fun’ and – contrary to our expectations - not too time-consuming. Users said that the use of smileys made it easier for them to quickly express their mood. Moreover, they added some playfulness. Being able to send pictures was also appreciated. Pictures made the feedback more concrete and prompted less need for long explanations, which saves time. One participant said that he preferred an app to an analogue diary (known as cultural probes). He said that it is easier to work with and more direct. Moreover, diaries can get lost easily in a work environment. The users liked the fact that there is a dialogue with the development team via a smart phone. They valued that their opinions are asked and taken seriously. Being part of such a research gave them the feeling that their feedback contributes to the improvement of the products they are working with.

Participants also had some suggestions for improving the app. The app should give better feedback when users answer a question or send a message. They would like to have confirmation that their message has reached the development team. Typing a lot of text on a smart phone was considered somewhat cumbersome. Even though the smiley’s and the inclusion of pictures

helped, they would also appreciate a speech-to-text tool to create text input.

As discussed earlier, keeping users motivated during a user research in a B2B context is a crucial aspect to get good results. Previous experiences also revealed that working with cultural probes in a business environment can be perceived as cumbersome for the participants. It can be regarded as an obligation which would diminish participants’ motivation to contribute to the research (Lucero and Mattelmaki, 2007; Lucero et al., 2004). However, we did not encounter that issue in our study. Participants were enthusiastic and their enthusiasm did not diminish during the study. We think that there were two reasons for it. Firstly, we have a long-term business relationship with the customers who participated in the study. Thus they were aware of the fact that the feedback they provide is taken seriously. It will improve the product and at the end they will benefit from it. Secondly, the feedback showed that use of smart phones made the process of providing feedback easier, more playful and more interesting for the participants. Furthermore, the app made the whole process more interactive. They got responses to their feedback, some extra questions and they were sent some tips helping them with their work. This interaction also prevented the motivation to drop.

Development team

Developers and designers working in the project were enthusiastic about the Tellme dashboard. They appreciated having direct access to the real-time feedback of users linked with product data. They liked seeing the general information in one view, but also expressed the need to be able to look into more details by clicking on specific items. They indicated that they would like to easily access the user researcher who is leading the study (the moderator) to be able to ask further questions to the users.

The development team was very interested in the real user quotes and pictures. They said that the user quotes reveal the motivation behind the feedback and also the nuances. User quotes and pictures linked to

product data made the information more vivid and trustworthy. The quotes helped the designers to create empathy with the users and get a better understanding of their experience with the product.

The use of visualizations at the home page was appreciated, because they helped the development team to get a quick overview and prioritize the user feedback. Especially the combination of quantitative and qualitative information triggered reactions and led to discussions in the team. For example: once the data showed that the printer was performing very well (no errors, high uptime), but one operator expressed a sad smiley. This unexpected combination triggered the development team to dive deeper into the user experience to find out what was causing the problem and the motivation behind the feedback. We think that Tellme was appreciated and embraced by the development team because it provided direct, clear user feedback linked to product data, and at the same time it gave them the opportunity to ask more details if they had further questions.

Our study showed that direct contact between development team and the users helped the team to understand the users and their feedback better. Normally, the development team does not have much contact with the users. Most of the user information available for the development team comes through service and sales departments because they have more direct contact with customers. However, this information is usually filtered as people make their own interpretations of what they see and hear.

Moderator

The moderator has an important role in analyzing, clustering and responding to the feedback. During this study, the moderator spent 2 hours per day on this. When the group of users becomes bigger, this will be more time consuming. We think that in the future, part of the moderation can be automated through the use of intelligent tags. As such the tool becomes less resource intensive. We believe however, that the 'human factor' of the moderator is essential in facilitating the dialogue between the users and the development team. They can guide discussions within the development team based on the feedback in the Tellme Dashboard. Next to that, users should not get the feeling they are receiving computer generated responses.

The challenge of the moderator role lies in the interpretation of the user feedback. It is important that this is done in an unbiased way, and that the development team trusts the objective and independent interpretation of this usability professional.

Improvements Tellme

Based on the feedback obtained from the users and development team, we improved the design of both the mobile application and the dashboard. Improvements were aimed making the visual design more readable, understandable and attractive (Figure 7) and therefore increasing the usability.

In the future, we foresee more improvements of the tool, for example making more use of technologies available within smart phones such as using GPS to track the movement of users in their work environment and using speech-to-text to facilitate text input.

Recommendations

Even though Tellme was developed within the context of Océ, we believe this tool has the opportunity to provide value to other companies working in a B2B context. Here we would like to share some recommendations regarding the adaptation and the use of the tool.

Firstly, both the app and the dashboard require some adaptation before it can be used in another context. To a big extent, the app can be used as is. The concepts used to collect the users' feedback, questions and moods can stay intact as the content of those is provided by the user. However, the survey questions and assignments should be reconsidered depending on the aim of the research and the type of product. Using the same concepts for similar kinds of assignments and updating just the content would make the adaptation easier. The same is also valid for the dashboard. Several concepts were used to represent information, such as the word cloud, the infographics and the quotes. Even if the content varies, the same concepts can still be used. Adapting the data logging system would be the most difficult part. For that the product itself should be designed as such at it sends usage data to the dashboard.

Conducting qualitative research with a large number of participants and analyzing all the information they provide is costly and labor intensive. Provided that the user research is done with a well defined target user group and the aim of the research is to get user feedback on the product under development (and not to assess hypotheses regarding variations within the target group), we think that using Tellme within a user research with 8 participants will lead to useful results. Eight participants can be distributed over different customer sites.

We also have some recommendations regarding how the research is conducted. As in every user research, it is important that the research goals are clearly communicated to the users and they are informed upfront about what is expected from them. If possible, we recommend having face to face contact with participants at the beginning of the research. It helps the researcher to get to know the users and the customer site and to build up rapport with the participants. It also gives room to the participants to ask questions about the tool and the research. It is also important to manage the expectations of the participants. It should be communicated upfront that Tellme is not a "WhatsApp" like application, but has a response-time similar to e-mail communication. Moreover, participants should be informed that the information and pictures they send via the app will be treated confidentially, for internal use only.

Figure 7. Improvements on the design (left-top: first prototype of the app, left-bottom: first prototype of the dashboard, right-top: second version of the app, right bottom: second version of the dashboard).

Conclusions

This paper has been concerned with conducting user research to inform the product development team in a B2B context. We have presented a new tool, Tellme, which has been developed by Océ to obtain user feedback on products that are under development. Through Tellme the development team can receive direct feedback from users, combined with real-time data from the print system they are using. This combination of both qualitative and quantitative information is a strong asset for the development team. It enables them to understand and empathize with the users they are designing for of the developed system. They can use the feedback in their discussions and during the process of decision making. Traditional methods for customer research often take much time to execute, analyze the results and share with the development team. Tellme however, provides real-time feedback in an effective way. As such the team can have access to the user feedback much earlier during development process which leads to well-motivated decisions and saves time and money for repair work.

Tellme also adds value for the customer. With Tellme the customers feel that their opinions are taken seriously and they are acknowledged as stakeholders in new product development. They appreciate the interactive dialogue and the response to their feedback. They feel they are contributing to the improvement of the products they will be using. This strengthening of relations between Océ and its customers is key in being successful in a B2B market

where products are investment goods and relations between producer and customer are long-term by definition.

To summarize, Tellme creates a dialogue between user, product data and developers. It helps us to understand what our customers really want. We can quickly react on their needs and that enables us to create the right products for them. Furthermore, the direct contact with our customers during product development and asking for their feedback strengthens customer relations. The combination of both outcomes enhances our business.

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